

Development and testing of graphene nanofilled sensors applied on composite aerospace structural items for structural dynamic and SHM applications

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COMPOSITE
BIOMATERIALI

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OUTLINE

- Motivation
- Transducers Design
- Experimental Tests
- Concluding Remarks

Motivation

Motivation

Condition-based monitoring

Cost vs. benefit

Direct Operative Cost depends upon transducers/equipment taken on board and benefit achieved by SHM

Motivation

Condition-based monitoring

Motivation

Use of thermoplastic composites (vs Thermoset)

Benefits

- Better vibration dampening
- Lightness
- Long shelf life
- Short processing time
- Recyclability
- Durability
 - Superior fatigue characteristics
 - Non abrasiveness
 - Toughness
 - Good corrosion resistance

Limitations

- High costs
 - Materials
 - Manufacturing
 - Tooling
- Restricted design and manufacturing know-how
- Low temperature for safe use
- Poor attitude of the matrix to disperse filler or to impregnate long reinforcing fibers

Thermoset transducer design and results

Transducer Design and Production Processes

from a previous work with the University of Rome La Sapienza

(12th EASN International Conference, 18-21 October 2022 – Barcellona)

A mixture of graphene nanoplates and epoxy resin is sprayed on a CFRP plate

Experimental Tests

Piezoresistive Sensors Array

Experimental Tests

Static behavior of Piezoresistive Sensors Array

Sensor ID	Substrate	R0 [k Ω]	GF @ $\epsilon=0.2\%$
S1	PC	340	15
S2	GFRC – FR4	3	6
S3	GFRC – FR4	26	6

Experimental Tests

Piezoresistive Sensors Array

S3 Piezoresistive

P3 Piezoelectric

SHM Structural Event Localizing: Acoustic Emission Technique by graphene-based sensors

The spacing d between sensors S1 & S2 or S1 & S3 must be much smaller than their distance D from the point of impact.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y_1 - y_A}{x_1 - x_A} \right) \approx \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y_2 - y_A}{x_2 - x_A} \right) \approx \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y_3 - y_A}{x_3 - x_A} \right)$$

$$\Delta t_{12} = \frac{d \cos \theta}{c(\theta)} \quad \Delta t_{13} = \frac{d \sin \theta}{c(\theta)}$$

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About the combination of high and low frequency methods for impact detection on aerospace components

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knowing
properties

Thermoplastic transducers design

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (1st attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

sensor sheet: raw materials and processing

Matrix: Polyamide 6 (PA6) Ravamid B NC by Ravago Group (d: 1.09 g/cc – HDT: 50 °C)

Filler: Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) supplied by Nanesa s.r.l. as G2Nan

Melt compounding: raw materials, pre-dried in an oven under vacuum for 3 h at a temperature of 100 °C, were extruded with the aid of a co-rotating twin screw extruder from Collin Teachline ZK25T (Ebersberg, Germany) by setting the screw speed at 40 rpm and the screw temperature profile 240–250–250–230–220 °C from the hopper to the die.

Compression molding: 2-mm thick sheets were obtained at 250 °C using a Collin GmbH (Edersberg, Germany) model P400E press and applying the following pressure profile over time: 2 min at 0 bar, 1 min at 5 bar, 1 min at 10 bar, 1 min at 20 bar and subsequent maintenance of the pressure during the cooling phase of the sample up to room temperature to prevent any shrinkage of the material.

SEM image of GNP lamellas

Twin-screw extruder

Lab press

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (2nd attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

sensor sheet: raw materials and processing

Dimension: 8.0 x 8.0 x 0.1 cm

Matrix: Polystyrene EDISTIR R850 E by ENI Versalis (d: 1,04 g/cc – MFR@200 °C/5 kg: 4 g/10 min - HDT: 85 °C)

Fillers: Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) by Nanesa s.r.l. as G2Nan and Single wall Carnon Nanotubes (SWCNTs) from Tuball (Average aspect ratio L/d: 3000).

SEM image of GNP lamellas

Melt compounding: raw materials were melt mixed with the aid of a Brabender-like apparatus (Rheocord EC of Haake Inc.) at 200 °C by setting the screw speed at 40 rpm for 5 min. With this procedure, two formulations were prepared including 3 wt% SWCNTs and 3 wt% SWCNTs+1 wt% GNPs, respectively.

Compression molding: 1-mm thick sheets were obtained at 200 °C using a Collin GmbH (Edersberg, Germany) model P400E press and applying the following pressure profile over time: 2 min at 0 bar, 1 min at 5 bar, 1 min at 10 bar, 1 min at 20 bar and subsequent maintenance of the pressure during the cooling phase of the sample up to room temperature to prevent any shrinkage of the material.

Brabender batch mixer

Lab press

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (2nd attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

- ❑ Dependence of material resistance from electrodes configurations
- ❑ Dependence of resistance from driving voltage
- ❑ Preliminary study of static non-linear electro-mechanical behaviour

First electrodes configuration

Second electrodes configuration

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (2nd attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

- ❑ Dependence of material resistance from electrodes configurations
- ❑ Dependence of resistance from driving voltage
- ❑ Preliminary study of static non-linear electro-mechanical behaviour

First electrodes configuration

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (2nd attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

- ❑ Dependence of material resistance from electrodes configurations
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First electrodes configuration

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (2nd attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

- ❑ Preliminary study of static and dynamic electro-mechanical behaviour on second electrodes configuration
- ❑ Continuous resistance and voltage recording during impacts and deformations

Thermoplastic Transducer Design and Production Processes (2nd attempt) (CNR-IPCB)

- Preliminary study of dynamic electro-mechanical behaviour

Concluding remarks

Current

- ❑ The use of massless transducer can strongly impact the benefit of SHM
- ❑ Graphene and CNT based thermoplastic piezoresistive sensors in their second configuration (polystyrene base material) demonstrated to be sensitive to static and dynamic strain
- ❑ Strong dependence on electrodes configurations – non-linear behaviour of resistance with voltage amplitude – hysteretic-type effects (condenser behaviour?)

Future

Strategies in progress with thermoplastic sensors

Measuring plate voltage and deformation during controlled load application

A triangular extensimeter has been applied at the center of one face of the small plate and more static deformation tests are scheduled to correlate deformations with corresponding resistance variations (Gauge factor evaluation)

Reducing the plate thickness (sensors use)

Produce a thin sheet of nano-filled polystyrene to be cut in different geometries producing sensors of different shapes and areas

Considering other thermoplastic matrices

Alternative thermoplastic matrices, mainly amorphous or with low degree of crystallinity to favor percolative states with minimal quantities of fillers, as thermoplastic polyurethanes or even derived from renewable sources.

Thank you for your attention...

A Smart design for a Clean Sky!

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